

Molecular and Morphological Characterization of *Aphelenchoides fuchsi* sp. n. (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae) Isolated from *Pinus eldarica* in Western Iran

MEHRAB ESMAEILI,¹ RAMIN HEYDARI,¹ MOZHGAN ZIAIE,² AND JIANFENG GU³

Abstract: *Aphelenchoides fuchsi* sp. n. is described and illustrated from bark and wood samples of a weakened Mondell pine in Kermanshah Province, western Iran. The new species has body length of 332 to 400 μm (females) and 365 to 395 μm (males). Lip region set off from body contour. The cuticle is weakly annulated, and there are four lines in the lateral field. The stylet is 8 to 10 μm long and has small basal swellings. The excretory pore is located ca one body diam. posterior to metacarpus valve or 51 to 62 μm from the head. The postuterine sac well developed (60–90 μm). Spicules are relatively short (15–16 μm in dorsal limb) with apex and rostrum rounded, well developed, and the end of the dorsal limb clearly curved ventrad like a hook. The male tail has usual three pairs of caudal papillae (2+2+2) and a well-developed mucro. The female tail is conical, terminating in a complicated step-like projection, usually with many tiny nodular protuberances. The new species belongs to the Group 2 sensu Shahina, category of *Aphelenchoides* species. Phylogenetic analysis based on small subunit (SSU) and partial large subunit (LSU) sequences of rRNA supported the morphological results.

Key words: *Aphelenchoides*, LSU, molecular, morphology, morphometrics, new species, phylogeny, SSU, taxonomy.

To find and prevent the spread of pests comprising pine wood nematode *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* (Steiner and Buhner, 1934) Nickle, 1970 in Iran, bark and wood samples must be sampled and inspected. So, during the past few years, a wide survey on dead or weakening pine trees in northern Iran was conducted and several species belonging to Aphelenchoididae Skarbilovich, 1947 were recovered and described: two new species of the genus *Ek-taphelenchoides* Baujard, 1984 (Pedram et al., 2012; Aliramaji et al., 2014); a new species of the genus *Bursaphelenchus* Fuchs, 1937 (Pedram et al., 2011); and a new species of the genus *Laimaphelenchus* Fuchs, 1937 (Asghari et al., 2012). Up to now, *B. xylophilus*, which has caused serious damage to the coniferous forests, has not been found in Iran.

The genus *Aphelenchoides* Fischer, 1894 contains at present more than 150 nominal species (Hunt, 2008) and tends to be greatly conserved in gross morphology, making species identification a very difficult task. Also, many of the description fall below modern standards. Currently, species discrimination in *Aphelenchoides* is mainly based on morphology and morphometrics. In recent years, several species of the genus were described related to the pine trees in different countries, e.g., China (Cheng et al., 2009; Zhuo et al., 2010) and the United States (Kaisa, 2000), and some species isolated from packaging wood in South Korea (Cui et al., 2011;

Fang et al., 2014b), India (Bina Chanu et al., 2013), South Africa (Wang et al., 2013), and Japan (Fang et al., 2014a). Recently a new species of *Aphelenchoides*, *Aphelenchoides huntensis* Esmaili, Fang, Li, and Heydari, 2016 is described in association with pine trees in Iran. It would be likely to find more *Aphelenchoides* species if other substrates (e.g., bark beetles) were examined with such attention.

During 2013 and 2014, we conducted some inspections on wood and bark samples from dead or weakened pine trees in western Iran. As a result, a new species of *Aphelenchoides* was isolated from a weakened Mondell pine tree (*Pinus eldarica* L.), which is described and figured in this paper as *Aphelenchoides fuchsi* sp. n. It is the second new species of *Aphelenchoides* that is described from Iran.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling, extraction, mounting, and drawing

Several bark and wood samples from weakened pine trees were collected from western Iran, which yielded an aphelenchid nematode belonging to the genus *Aphelenchoides*. The nematodes were recovered from the wood samples by soaking a small amount of wood in water for 48 hr and handpicked under a stereomicroscope model Olympus SZH (Japan). The nematodes were heat killed by adding boiling 4% formalin solution and then transferred to anhydrous glycerin and mounted in permanent slides according to the method by De Grisse (1969). Permanent slides were prepared and studied using a light microscope (Nikon E200). Drawings were made using a drawing tube attached to the same microscope, and photographs of live nematodes were taken by a digital camera attached to the microscope.

DNA extraction, polymerase chain reaction, and sequencing

A single live nematode specimen of *A. fuchsi* sp. n. was picked out, examined on a temporary slide, and then transferred to a small drop of AE buffer (10 mM Tris-Cl, 0.5 mM EDTA, pH 9.0; Qiagen Inc., Valencia, CA) on a clean slide and squashed using a clean cover slip. The

Received for publication October 21, 2015.

¹Department of Plant Protection, College of Agriculture and Natural resources, University of Tehran, Karaj, Iran.

²Faculty of Agriculture, Roudchen Branch, Islamic Azad University (IAU), Roudchen, Iran.

³Technical Centre, Ningbo Entry-exit Inspection and Quarantine Bureau, 9 Mayuan Road, Ningbo 315012, Zhejiang, PR China.

The authors thank the University of Tehran for financial supports, Shahab Esmaili (University of Tehran) for his help with sampling and Yiwu Fang for helpful comments. The Iranian authors are very grateful to Mr. Kaveh Khosraviyani (Expert of Central Laboratory of Genetic and Biotechnology Department of Agriculture and Natural Resources University of Tehran, Iran) for his technical help. The Chinese author would like to thank Ningbo Natural Science Foundation (2014A610197), Ningbo Science and Technology Innovation Team (2015C110018) and Chinese National Science and Technology Support Program (2012BAK11B03).

E-mail: rheydari@ut.ac.ir.

This paper was edited by Zafar A. Handoo.

suspension was collected by adding 20 µl AE buffer. The DNA samples were stored at -20°C until used as polymerase chain reaction (PCR) templates. For the first fragment of 18S, the forward primer 1096F (5'-GGT AAT TCT GGA GCT AAT AC-3') was used in combination with the reverse primer 1912R (5'-TTT ACG GTC AGA ACT AGG G-3'), and the second fragment was amplified with forward primers 1813F (5'-CTG CGT GAG AGG TGA AAT-3') and reverse primer 2646R (5'-GCT ACC TTG TTA CGA CTT TT-3') (Holterman et al., 2006). The D2-D3 expansion segments of 28S rRNA gene were amplified using forward primer D2A (5'-ACA AGT ACC GTG AGG GAA AGT TG-3') and reverse primer D3B (5'-TCG GAA GGA ACC AGC TAC TA-3') (Nunn, 1992). Polymerase chain reaction was performed in a final volume of 25 µl PCR mixture and contained 12.5 µl 2X GoTaq DNA polymerase mix (Promega Corporation, Madison, WI), each of a 1.2 µl forward and reverse primers solution (5 pM), 8 µl distilled water, and 2 µl of a 100 times-diluted crude DNA extract. The following PCR profile was used: 94°C for 5 min; 5 × (94°C, 30 sec; 45°C, 30 sec; and 72°C, 70 sec) followed by 35 × (94°C, 30 sec; 54°C, 30 sec; 72°C, 70 sec) and 72°C, 5 min. The PCR products were purified and sequenced directly for both strands using the same

primers with an ABI 3730XL sequencer (MacroGen Corporation, Seoul, South Korea). The newly obtained sequences was submitted to GenBank database under accession numbers KT003986 (18S) and KT003987 (28S).

The obtained sequences of the partial 18S and partial 28S D2-D3 region ribosomal DNA (rDNA) gene of *A. fuchsi* sp. n. were compared with those of other aphelenchids species available in GenBank (see Table 1 for selected sequences of SSU and Table 2 for LSU D2-D3) using BLAST homology search program. Outgroup was chosen according to previous published data (Fang et al., 2014a, 2014b; Esmaeili et al., 2016). The newly obtained and published sequences were aligned using MAFFT ver. 7 (Katoh et al., 2002) with default parameters. Sequence alignment was edited using BioEdit (Hall, 1999). The best fitted model of DNA evolution was obtained using jModelTest2 (Darriba et al., 2012) with the Akaike information criterion. The Akaike-supported model, the base frequency, the proportion of invariable sites, and the gamma distribution shape parameters and substitution rates in the Akaike information criterion were then used in phylogenetic analyses. The tree topology was confirmed using MrBayes 3.2.3 (Ronquist and Huelsenbeck, 2003) with four chains (three heated and one cold). The number of generations for the total analysis was set to 10 million, with the chain sampled every

TABLE 1. Species used for analysis of phylogenetic relationships and the accession numbers for SSU sequences deposited in GenBank.

Species	Accession number	Authors	Species	Accession number	Authors
<i>Aphelenchoides fuchsi</i> sp. n.	KT003986	Present paper	<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	DQ901553	Subbotin et al., 2006
<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	AY508035	Ye et al., 2007	<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	EU287591	Zhao et al., 2008
<i>Aphelenchoides bicaudatus</i>	HQ283351	Huang et al., 2012	<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	GU337995	Cui et al., 2011
<i>Aphelenchoides blastophthorus</i>	JQ957879	Rybarczyk-Mydłowska et al., 2012	<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	GU337994	Cui et al., 2011
<i>Aphelenchoides blastophthorus</i>	AY284646	Holterman et al., 2006	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i>	AB368918	Unpublished
<i>Aphelenchoides fragariae</i>	DQ901551	Subbotin et al., 2006	<i>Aprutides guidetti</i>	KJ636424	Unpublished
<i>Aphelenchoides fragariae</i>	AB067755	Unpublished	<i>Ficophagus aureus</i>	DQ912922	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides fujianensis</i>	FJ520227	Zhuo et al., 2010	<i>Ficophagus benjamina</i>	KJ638352	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides huntensis</i>	KR864863	Esmaeili et al., 2016	<i>Ficophagus centerae</i>	DQ912923	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides macronucleatus</i>	FJ235883	Unpublished	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638366	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides paradaliensis</i>	GU337993	Cui et al., 2011	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638358	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides ritzemabosi</i>	DQ901554	Subbotin et al., 2006	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638361	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides rotundicaudatus</i>	KFF772858	Fang et al., 2014b	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638364	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides saprophilus</i>	FJ040408	Holterman et al., 2006	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638370	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides subtenuis</i>	JQ957891	Rybarczyk-Mydłowska et al., 2012	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	EU038299	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides varicaudatus</i>	HQ283351	Huang et al., 2012	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638360	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides xui</i>	FJ643487	Wang et al., 2013	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638357	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	JQ957884	Rybarczyk-Mydłowska et al., 2012	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KM817192	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	AY284646	Holterman et al., 2006	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KC526928	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	FJ040409	Holterman et al., 2006	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	AB904757	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	FJ040410	Holterman et al., 2006	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638354	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	JQ957885	Huang et al., 2012	<i>Laimaphelenchus heidelbergi</i>	EU287587	Zhao et al., 2008
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	GU337997	Cui et al., 2011	<i>Laimaphelenchus belgradiensis</i>	KF881745	Oro, 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	GU337999	Cui et al., 2011	<i>Laimaphelenchus penardi</i>	AY593918	Holterman et al., 2006
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	GU337998	Cui et al., 2011	<i>Laimaphelenchus perissii</i>	EU287590	Zhao et al., 2008
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	JQ957883	Huang et al., 2012	<i>Martininema guanzagzhouensis</i>	DQ912924	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	AB661626	Unpublished	<i>Robustodoros megadorus</i>	KC687094	Unpublished
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	GU337996	Cui et al., 2011	<i>Schistonchus caprifici</i>	GU190764	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	EU287589	Zhao et al., 2008	<i>Schistonchus</i> sp.	HM151003	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	DQ901550	Subbotin et al., 2006	-	-	-

TABLE 2. Species used for analysis of phylogenetic relationships and the accession numbers for LSU D2-D3 sequences deposited in GenBank.

Species	Accession number	Authors	Species	Accession number	Authors
<i>Aphelenchoides fuchsi</i> sp. n.	KT003987	Present paper	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	AB535556	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	EU325682	Zhao et al., 2008	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	AB535565	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides fragariae</i>	EU325684	Zhao et al., 2008	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KC526929	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides huntensis</i>	KR864862	Esmaeili et al., 2016	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KM817193	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides rotundicaudatus</i>	KF772859	Fang et al., 2014b	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638372	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides stellatus</i>	KF638651	Fang et al., 2014a	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638376	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides stammeri</i>	AM396582	Unpublished	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638377	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides varicaudatus</i>	HQ283353	Huang et al., 2012	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638378	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides xui</i>	FJ643488	Wang et al., 2013	<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	KJ638384	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides xylocopae</i>	AB434933	Kanzaki et al., 2008	<i>Laimaphelenchus australis</i>	EU287600	Zhao et al., 2008
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	DQ328682	Subbotin et al., 2006	<i>Laimaphelenchus belgradiensis</i>	KF881746	Oro, 2015
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	EU287597	Zhao et al., 2008	<i>Laimaphelenchus deconincki</i>	KF998578	Unpublished
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	EU287599	Zhao et al., 2008	<i>Laimaphelenchus heidelbergi</i>	EU287595	Zhao et al., 2008
<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp.	EU084037	Unpublished	<i>Laimaphelenchus persicus</i>	JN006987	Asghari et al., 2012
<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i>	AB368536	Kanzaki et al., 2008	<i>Laimaphelenchus perissii</i>	EU287598	Zhao et al., 2008
<i>Ficophagus altermacrophylla</i>	AB535534	Davies et al., 2015	<i>Laimaphelenchus</i> sp.	AB368539	Kanzaki et al., 2008
<i>Ficophagus aureus</i>	DQ912926	Davies et al., 2015	<i>Laimaphelenchus</i> sp.	KJ472144	Unpublished
<i>Ficophagus benjamina</i>	AB535558	Davies et al., 2015	<i>Laimaphelenchus</i> sp.	KJ567061	Miraeiz et al., 2015
<i>Ficophagus benjamina</i>	AB535553	Davies et al., 2015	<i>Martininema fistulosus</i>	KC250363	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Ficophagus centrae</i>	DQ912928	Davies et al., 2015	<i>Martininema guanzagzhouensis</i>	DQ912927	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Ficophagus microcapus</i>	GU392234	Davies et al., 2015	<i>Martininema</i> sp.	KM817190	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Ficophagus laevigatus</i>	DQ912926	Davies et al., 2015	<i>Schistonchus caprifici</i>	GU190765	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Ficophagus virens</i>	AB535565	Davies et al., 2015	<i>Schistonchus hirtus</i>	GQ849473	Davies et al., 2015
<i>Ficophagus</i> sp.	AB535555	Davies et al., 2015	<i>Schistonchus macrophylla</i>	AB535531	Davies et al., 2015

1,000 generations and the burn-in value was 25%. The Markov Chain Monte Carlo method within a Bayesian framework was used to estimate the posterior probabilities of the phylogenetic trees using 50% majority rule (Larget and Simon, 1999). The consensus trees were selected to represent the phylogenetic relationships with branch length and support level and visualized using TreeGraph 2 (Stöver and Müller, 2010).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

*Aphelenchoides fuchsi** sp. n. (Figs. 1,2).

Measurements

See Table 3.

Description

Females: Body is cylindrical, straight, somewhat ventrally arcuate when heat relaxed. Cuticle weakly annulated, lateral field with four incisures (i.e., three ridges). Lip region is rounded, offset, ca 3 to 3.5 μm high, and 6 to 7 μm broad. Stylet with small basal swellings, procorpus cylindrical. Median bulb is strongly developed, almost rectangular, with conspicuous valve situated more or less centrally. Nerve ring is situated at ca half metacarpus (median bulb) length posterior to it. Pharyngointestinal junction is immediately posterior to metacarpus. Pharyngeal gland lobe is slender, ca five to six body diam. long, overlapping intestine dorsally. Excretory pore is at level of

nerve ring or opposite the posterior level of the nerve ring, the position varying from 1/2 to 2/3 metacarpus length behind metacarpus. Hemizonid is faint, situated ca two to three times metacarpus diam. posterior to excretory pore. Monodelphic, ovary is outstretched anteriorly, developing oocytes in single row. Oviduct connecting ovary and spermatheca. Spermatheca is elongate, containing compressed disklike or oblong sperm in single row. Vagina is directed anteriorly. Vulva is transverse, with slightly raised lips, and vulval flap is absent. Postuterine sac is well developed, extending for about 71% to 90% of vulva to anus distance, often containing sperm. Rectum and anus are visible. Tail is conical, terminating in a complicated step-like projection, usually with many tiny nodular protuberances.

Males: They are much less common than females; body slender, cylindrical, and J-shaped when heat relaxed. Anterior region and cuticle are similar to female. Testis is single, anteriorly outstretched, locating left of intestine, occupying 53.4% to 66.2% of body length. Lips of cloacal opening protruding slightly. Spicules are arcuate, relatively short, and apex and rostrum are rounded and well developed, end of dorsal limb is clearly curved ventrally. Gubernaculum is absent. Tail is conical, bearing a short sharp mucro ca 1.5 to 2 μm long. Three pairs of subventral caudal papillae are present: first pair located just posterior to cloacal aperture, second pair in mid-tail region, and third pair just anterior to tail end. Bursa is absent.

Diagnosis and relationships

Aphelenchoides fuchsi sp. n. is characterized by body length of 332 to 400 μm (females) and 365 to 395 μm (males). Lip region with distinct constriction from the

* The new species is named in honor of Prof. Gilbert Fuchs, a pioneering scientist in the systematics of aphelenchids.

FIG. 1. Line drawing of *Aphelenchoides fuchsi* sp. n. A: Female anterior region; B: Female tail; C: Male posterior body showing caudal papillae; D: Male entire body; E: Female entire body; F: Female vulva to body-end; G: Metacarpus region and showing excretory pore; H: Female anterior head; I: Spicule in detail; J: Lateral field. (All scales in 15 μ m.)

rest body. Cuticle with four lateral lines. Medium sized (8–10 μ m) stylet with small basal swellings. The excretory pore is located ca one body diam. to posterior of metacarpus valve. The female tail is conical and terminates in a complicated step-like projection, usually with many tiny nodular protuberances. Spicules are relatively short (15–16 μ m in dorsal limb) with the apex and rostrum rounded and well developed, the end of the dorsal limb is clearly curved ventrally like a hook (Fig. 2G,F).

Aphelenchoides fuchsi sp. n. has a tail terminus with tiny nodular protuberances in female. According to the category of *Aphelenchoides* species sensu Shahina (1996), the new species belongs to Group 2, which is defined as having the female tail terminus with “one or sometimes

two mucronate structures.” On the basis of the four lateral lines, stylet length, conical female tail, and shape of spicules, the new species appears morphologically most similar to four species from Group 2 including *Aphelenchoides arcticus* Sanwal, 1965, *Aphelenchoides blastophthorus* Franklin, 1952, *Aphelenchoides saprophilus* Franklin, 1957, and *Aphelenchoides xui* Wang, Wang, Gu, Wang, and Li, 2013. It is also similar to three species from Group 4 including *Aphelenchoides franklini* Singh, 1969, *Aphelenchoides gynotylurus* Timm and Franklin, 1969, and *Aphelenchoides marinus* Timm and Franklin, 1969.

Aphelenchoides fuchsi sp. n. differs from *A. arcticus*, *A. blastophthorus*, *A. franklini*, *A. gynotylurus*, *A. marinus*, and

FIG. 2. Light micrographs of *Aphelenchoides fuchsi* sp. n. A: Female posterior body showing post-uterine sac by arrow; B: Female head and stylet in detail; C: Female pharynx region showing excretory pore and hemizonoid by arrow; D: Metacarpus and position of excretory system; E: Female genital tract; F: Spicules in detail; G: Male posterior body showing spicules and papillae arrangement by arrows; H: Lateral field; I, J: Female tail. (A,C-E = 20; B,F-J = 10 μ m.)

A. saprophilus by the female tail terminus, i.e., ending of a step-like projection/or offset mucro with many tiny nodular protuberances in *A. fuchsi* sp. n. vs. a shallow constriction narrowed sharply with a very fine mucro at the tip (*A. arcticus*), tapering to a simple conspicuous mucro (*A. blastophthorus*), a simple pointed ventral mucro (*A. franklini*), ending in a digitate to blunt/or sometimes sickle-shaped mucro (*A. gynotylurus*), acutely conical tapering to a point that is sometimes truncate/or subacute (*A. marinus*), and a short ventral mucro (*A. saprophilus*).

Moreover, *A. fuchsi* sp. n. differs from *A. arcticus* by the male spicule shape (dorsal limb with a hook-like tip vs. smoothly rounded tip) and the offset vs. nonoffset

lip region. It differs from *A. blastophthorus* by the shorter body length of female (320–400 vs. 680–900 μ m), the shorter stylet length (8–10 vs. 14–19 μ m), lower a ratio (25–32 vs. 40–41), and the male spicule length in dorsal limb (15–16 vs. 24–31 μ m). It differs from *A. franklini* by having a longer postuterine sac (5.5 vs. 2.5 times the body width), the shorter body length of female (320–400 vs. 556 μ m), the male spicule length and shape in dorsal limb (15–16 μ m with clearly curved ventrad like a hook vs. 23 μ m long, with slightly curved and rounded tip). It differs from *A. gynotylurus* by having the shorter stylet length (8–10 vs. 15–16 μ m), shorter body length of female (332–400 vs. 490–650 μ m), and the male

TABLE 3. Morphometrics of *Aphelenchoides fuchsi* sp. n.

Character	Male		Female
	Holotype	Paratypes	Paratypes
n	–	5	15
L	367	377.8 ± 12.2 (365–395)	382.3 ± 20.3 (332–400)
a	30.6	30.5 ± 0.8 (29.4–31.7)	28.3 ± 2.3 (25.1–32.9)
b	6.6	6.6 ± 0.2 (6.5–6.9)	6.8 ± 0.3 (6.4–7.3)
b'	2.8	2.8 ± 0.1 (2.7–3.0)	3.4 ± 0.3 (3.0–3.8)
c	15.3	13.7 ± 1.1 (12.7–15.3)	12.8 ± 0.8 (11.8–14.3)
c'	1	1.1 ± 0.1 (1.0–1.2)	4.6 ± 0.5 (3.8–5.3)
V or T	66.2	53.9 ± 5.4 (53.4–66.2)	68.1 ± 2.6 (64.4–74.5)
Lip region height	3	3.1 ± 0.2 (3.0–3.5)	3.1 ± 0.2 (3.0–3.5)
Lip region width	5	4.2 ± 0.4 (4.0–5.0)	6.2 ± 0.4 (6.0–7.0)
Stylet length	9	9.0 ± 0.4 (8.5–9.5)	9.2 ± 0.7 (8.0–10.0)
Conus length	4	3.9 ± 0.2 (3.5–4.0)	3.9 ± 0.3 (3.5–4.5)
m ^a	44.4	43.3 ± 1.6 (41.2–44.4)	42.7 ± 1.9 (40–45)
Body diam.	12	12.4 ± 0.5 (12.0–13.0)	13.6 ± 1.3 (11.0–15.0)
Body diam. at median bulb	11	11.1 ± 0.2 (11.5–11.5)	11.7 ± 1.0 (10.0–13.0)
Median bulb width	6	6.5 ± 0.9 (6.0–8.0)	7.7 ± 0.6 (7.0–8.0)
Median bulb length	12	11.2 ± 0.4 (11.0–12.0)	11.8 ± 0.8 (11.0–12.5)
Median bulb length/diam. ratio	2	1.7 ± 0.2 (1.4–2.0)	1.5 ± 0.0 (1.5–1.6)
Excretory pore from anterior end	57	58.8 ± 3.4 (55–64)	58.5 ± 3.6 (51–62)
Hemizonid from anterior end	95	88 ± 6.1 (84–95)	76 ± 1.6 (74–78)
Ovary length or testis	243	224 ± 19.2 (195–243)	162.6 ± 25.1 (128–210)
Postuterine sac	–	–	74 ± 8.6 (60–90)
Vulva to anus distance	–	–	91.8 ± 8.8 (69–100)
Postuterine sac length/vulva to anus (%)	–	–	80.7 ± 6.9 (74.7–90.0)
Anal (cloacal) body diameter	8	9.0 ± 0.7 (8.0–10.0)	5.5 ± 0.5 (6.0–7.0)
Tail length	24	27.8 ± 2.3 (24–30)	29.9 ± 2.1 (25.0–33.0)
Spicule (dorsal limb)	16	15.6 ± 0.5 (15.0–16.0)	–
Spicule (ventral limb)	9	8.7 ± 0.4 (8.0–9.0)	–
Spicule (curved median line)	11	10.7 ± 0.4 (10.0–11.0)	–
Spicule (chord)	10	9.4 ± 0.4 (9.0–10.0)	–
Mucro	–	–	1.8 ± 0.4 (1.5–2.0)

All measurements are in μm and in the form: mean \pm SD (range).

^a Length of conus as percentage of total stylet length.

spicule length in dorsal limb (15–16 μm long, with clearly curved ventrad like a hook vs. 21–24 μm , smoothly rounded tip). It differs from *A. marinus* by having the shorter body length of female (332–400 vs. 570–860 μm), the shorter stylet length (8–10 vs. 13–14 μm), and the male spicule length in dorsal limb (15–16 vs. 24–25 μm). It differs from *A. saprophilus* by the shorter body length of female (332–400 vs. 454–623 μm) and the male spicule length in dorsal limb (15–16 vs. 23 μm). Also, it can be distinguished from *A. xui* by the shorter body length of female (332–400 vs. 548–882 μm), the shorter stylet length (8–10 vs. 11.1–13.2 μm), and the male spicule length in dorsal limb (15–16 vs. 21.7–33.4 μm).

The female tail of *A. fuchsi* sp. n. is also similar to some *Laimaphelenchus* species. *Laimaphelenchus* contains two groups of species: one with a vulval flap and one without (Hunt, 1993). Moreover, *Laimaphelenchus* is also characterized by the vagina either having a cuticular annulus at the point where it joins the uterus or is surrounded by a relatively thick refractile tube or strong musculature (Zhao et al., 2007). Considering these two morphological characters (absence of vulval flap and vagina structure in new species), the new species was far from *Laimaphelenchus* and therefore placed in *Aphelenchoides*. In addition, the entire *Aphelenchoides* and *Laimaphelenchus* groups are in

urgent need of revision based on sequences of full-length SSU rDNA sequences or other informative loci combined with detailed morphological diagnostic characters.

Type habitat and locality

The type population was recovered from bark and wood samples of a weakened Mondell pine tree (*P. eldarica*) in vicinity of Cheshmeh-e-Nezamei, city of Gilan-e-Gharb, Kermanshah Province, western Iran (GPS coordinates: N 33°59', E 46°12'; 1,248 m above sea level).

Remark

Aphelenchoides fuchsi sp. n. was successfully cultured on *Botryotinia fuckeliana* growing on Potato Dextrose Agar. The nematode was not culturable on *Botrytis cinerea*.

Type material

Holotype female, two paratype females, and two paratype males (Slides AAF002 and AAF003) were deposited in nematode collection of the Department of Plant Protection, College of Agriculture and Natural Resources, University of Tehran, Iran. Three paratype females were deposited at each of the following collections: CABI, Egham, United Kingdom; USDA

FIG. 4. Phylogenetic relationships of *Aphelenchoides fuchsi* sp. n. and aphelenchid nematodes based on partial 28S D2-D3 region rDNA gene. The 10001st Bayesian tree inferred from 28S D2-D3 region rDNA gene under TIM3 + I + G model ($\ln L = -14298.9428$; $\text{freqA} = 0.2097$; $\text{freqC} = 0.1828$; $\text{freqG} = 0.3009$; $\text{freqT} = 0.3065$; $R(a) = 0.8529$; $R(b) = 3.2742$; $R(c) = 1.0000$; $R(d) = 0.8529$; $R(e) = 4.4607$; $R(f) = 1.0000$; $\text{Pinva} = 0.1440$; $\text{Shape} = 0.6640$). *Aphelenchus avenae* served as the outgroup species. Posterior probability values exceeding 50% are given on appropriate clades.

Moreover, this genus has few morphologically diagnostic taxonomic characters (Kanzaki, 2006).

In general, the morphology of the tail tip of *A. fuchsi* sp. n. is similar to some described species of the genus in Group 2, according to the category of *Aphelenchoides* species sensu Shahina (1996), which is defined as having the female tail terminus with “one or sometimes two mucronate structures” but this structure, in the new species, is not simple and the female tail terminus have a step-like projection with many tiny nodular protuberances. Moreover, the male spicule shape (dorsal limb with a hook-like tip) is a diagnostic character between similar species of the genus.

Recently, several species of the genus were described and molecularly studied (Cui et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2013; Fang et al., 2014a, 2014b; Esmaili et al., 2016). Molecular characterization and phylogenetic analyses based on rDNA region sequences including 18S, internal transcribed spacer regions, and the D2-D3 expansion segments of 28S can assist in accurate identification of the species, although with the important proviso that most nominal *Aphelenchoides* species lack such reliable information.

Small subunit of rDNA contains sufficient phylogenetic signal for the identification of *Aphelenchoides* species (De Ley et al., 2006; Zhao et al., 2008; Van Megen et al., 2009) and have been shown to be more useful for species identification compared to D2-D3 expansion segments of 28S rRNA and internal transcribed spacer rRNA, as both of these markers showed more species variability than did partial 18S rDNA (Zhao et al 2008; Esmaili et al., 2016).

This is the second new species of the genus from Iran to be described and sequenced. *Aphelenchoides fuchsi* sp. n. was found in bark of a weakened pine tree but not in its wood. Therefore, the new species appears to be feeding on fungi or lichens growing on the bark of the tree.

LITERATURE CITED

Aliramaji, F., Pourjam, E., Atighi, M. R., Ye, W., Roshan-Bakhsh, A., and Pedram, M. 2014. Description of *Ektaphelenchoides poinari* sp. n. (Nematoda: Ektaphelenchinae) from Iran with compendium of the valid species of the genus *Ektaphelenchoides* Baujard, 1984. Russian Journal of Nematology 22:11–22.

Asghari, R., Pourjam, E., Heydari, R., and Zhao, Z. 2012. *Laimaphelenchus persicus* n. sp. (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae) from Iran. Zootaxa 3325:59–67.

Bina Chanu, L., Mohilal, N., Victoria, L., and Shah, M. M. 2013. Eight known species of *Aphelenchoides* nematodes with description of a new species from Manipur, India. Journal of Parasitic Diseases 39:225–233.

Cheng, W., Hou, H., and Lin, M. S. 2009. *Aphelenchoides dalianensis* sp. nov. (Nematoda, Aphelenchoididae) from *Pinus thunbergii* from China. Acta Zootaxonomica Sinica 34:401–406.

Cui, R., Zhuo, K., Wang, H., and Liao, J. 2011. *Aphelenchoides paradalianensis* n. sp. (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae) isolated at Guangzhou, China, in packaging wood from South Korea. Zootaxa 2864:57–64.

Darriba, D., Taboada, G. L., Doallo, R., and Posada, D. 2012. jModelTest 2: More models, new heuristics and parallel computing. Nature Methods 9:772.

De Grisse, A. T. 1969. Redescription ou modifications de quelques techniques utilisées dans l'étude de nématodes phytoparasitaires. Mededelingen Rijksfaculteit LandbouwWetenschappen Gent 34:315–359.

- De Ley, P., Decraemer, W., and Abebe, E. 2006. Introduction: Summary of present knowledge and research addressing the ecology and taxonomy of freshwater nematodes. Pp. 3–30 in E. Abebe, I. Andrassy, and W. Traunspurger, eds. *Freshwater nematodes, ecology and taxonomy*. Wallingford, United Kingdom: CABI Publishing.
- Esmacili, M., Fang, Y., Li, H., and Heydari, R. 2016. Description of *Aphelenchoides humtensis* sp. n. (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae) isolated from *Pinus sylvestris* in western Iran. *Nematology* (in press). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/15685411-00002963>.
- Fang, Y., Gu, J., Wang, X., and Li, H. 2014a. Description of *Aphelenchoides stellatus* n. sp. (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae) found in packaging wood from Japan. *Nematology* 16:621–630.
- Fang, Y., Gu, J., Wang, X., and Li, H. 2014b. Description of *Aphelenchoides rotundicaudatus* n. sp. (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae) found in packaging wood from South Korea. *Nematology* 16:751–760.
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). 2003. Guidelines for regulating wood packaging material in international trade. International Standards for Phytosanitary Measures (ISPM), No. 15. Rome, Italy: FAO.
- Franklin, M. T. 1952. A disease of *Scabiosa caucasica* caused by the nematode *Aphelenchoides blastophthorus* n. sp. *Annals of Applied Biology* 39:54–60.
- Franklin, M. T. 1957. *Aphelenchoides composticola* n. sp. and *A. saprophilus* n. sp. from mushroom compost and rotting plant tissues. *Nematologica* 2:306–313.
- Hall, T. A. 1999. BioEdit: A user-friendly biological sequence alignment editor and analysis program for windows 95/98/NT. *Nucleic Acids Symposium Series* 41:95–98.
- Holterman, M., van der Wurff, A., van den Elsen, S., van Megen, H., Holovachov, T. M. O., Bakker, J., and Helder, J. 2006. Phylum-wide analysis of SSU rDNA reveals deep phylogenetic relationships among nematodes and accelerated evolution toward crown clades. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 23:1792–1800.
- Huang, R. E., Ye, W., Liang, J., Lu, Q., and Zhang, X. Y. 2012. *Tylaphelenchus jiaae* n. sp. and *Aphelenchoides varicaudatus* (Nematoda: Aphelenchoidinae) from Simao pine in Yunnan Province, China. *Nematology* 14:93–108.
- Hunt, D. J. 1993. Aphelenchida, longidoridae and trichodoridae: Their systematics and bionomics. Pp. 352. Wallingford, United Kingdom: CAB International.
- Hunt, D. J. 2008. A checklist of the Aphelenchoidea (Nematoda: Tylenchida). *Journal of Nematode Morphology and Systematics* 10:99–135.
- Kaisa, T. R. 2000. *Aphelenchoides microstylus* n. sp. and *Seinura onodagensis* n. sp. (Nematoda: Aphelenchida) from New York. *Journal of Nematology* 32:396–402.
- Kanzaki, N. 2006. Description of *Aphelenchoides xylocopae* n. sp. (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae), the first observed association between nematodes and carpenter bees. *Nematology* 8:555–562.
- Kanzaki, N., Giblin-Davis, R. M., Cardoza, Y. J., Ye, W., Raffa, K. F., and Center, B. J. 2008. *Bursaphelenchus rufipennis* n. sp. (Nematoda: Parasitaphelenchinae) and redescription of *Ektaphelenchus obtusus* (Nematoda: Ektaphelenchinae), associates from nematangia on the hind wings of *Dendroctonus rufipennis* (Coleoptera: Scolytidae). *Nematology* 10(6):925–955.
- Katoh, K., Misawa, K., Kuma, K., and Miyata, T. 2002. MAFFT: A novel method for rapid multiple sequence alignment based on fast Fourier transform. *Nucleic Acids Resources* 30:3059–3066.
- Larget, B., and Simon, D. L. 1999. Markov chain Monte Carlo algorithms for the Bayesian analysis of phylogenetic trees. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 16:750–759.
- Miraeiz, E., Heydari, R., Tanha Maafi, Z., and Bert, W. 2015. *Laimaphelenchus hyrcanus* n. sp. (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae), a new species from northern Iran. *Zootaxa* 3915(4):591–600.
- Nunn, G. B. 1992. Nematode molecular evolution. Ph.D. dissertation, University of Nottingham, United Kingdom.
- Oro, V. 2015. Description of *Laimaphelenchus belgradiensis* sp. nov. (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae) and its phylogenetic and systematic position within Aphelenchoidea. *European Journal of Plant Pathology* 142(1):13–23.
- Pedram, M., Pourjam, E., Atighi, M. R., Ye, W., and Houshmand, A. 2012. *Ektaphelenchoides sylvestris* sp. nov. (Nematoda: Ektaphelenchinae) from Iran. *Annales Zoologici* 62:325–329.
- Pedram, M., Pourjam, E., Ye, W., Atighi, M. R., Robbins, R. T., and Ryss, A. 2011. Description of *Bursaphelenchus mazandaranense* sp. n. (Nematoda: Parasitaphelenchidae) from Iran. *Russian Journal of Nematology* 19:121–129.
- Ronquist, F., and Huelsenbeck, J. P. 2003. MrBAYES3: Bayesian phylogenetic inference under mixed models. *Bioinformatics* 19:1572–1574.
- Rybarczyk-Mydlowska, K., Mooyman, P., van Megen, H., van den Elsen, S., Vervoort, M., Veenhuizen, P., van Doorn, J., Dees, R., Karssen, G., Bakker, J., and Helder, J. 2012. Small subunit ribosomal DNA-based phylogenetic analysis of foliar nematodes (*Aphelenchoides* spp.) and their quantitative detection in complex DNA backgrounds. *Phytopathology* 102:1153–1160.
- Sanwal, K. C. 1965. Two new species of the genus *Aphelenchoides* Fischer, 1894 (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae) from the Canadian Arctic. *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 43:933–940.
- Shahina, F. 1996. A diagnostic compendium of the genus *Aphelenchoides* Fischer, 1894 (Nematoda: Aphelenchida) with some new records of the group from Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Nematology* 14:1–32.
- Singh, S. P. 1969. A new species of the genus *Aphelenchoides* Fischer, 1894 (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae) from rootlets of radish (*Raphanus sativus*) in Lucknow. *Journal of Helminthology* 43:193–196.
- Steiner, G., and Buhner, E. M. 1934. *Aphelenchoides xylophilus*, n. sp. a nematode associated with blue-stain and other fungi in timber. *Journal of Agricultural Research* 48:949–951.
- Stöver, B. C., and Müller, K. F. 2010. TreeGraph 2: Combining and visualizing evidence from different phylogenetic analyses. *BMC Bioinformatics* 11:7.
- Subbotin, S. A., Sturhan, D., Chizhov, V. N., Vovlas, N., and Baldwin, J. G. 2006. Phylogenetic analysis of Tylenchida Thorne, 1949 as inferred from D2 and D3 expansion fragments of the 28S rRNA gene sequences. *Nematology* 8(3):455–474.
- Timm, R. W., and Franklin, M. T. 1969. Two marine species of *Aphelenchoides*. *Nematologica* 15:370–375.
- Van Megen, H., van den Elsen, S., Holterman, M., Karssen, G., Mooyman, P., Bongers, T., Holovachov, O., Bakker, J., and Helder, J. 2009. A phylogenetic tree of nematodes based on about 1200 full-length small subunit ribosomal DNA sequences. *Nematology* 11:927–950.
- Wang, X., Wang, P., Gu, J., Wang, J., and Li, H. 2013. Description of *Aphelenchoides xui* n. sp. (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae) in packaging wood from South Africa. *Nematology* 15:279–289.
- Ye, W., Giblin-Davis, R. M., B Raasch, H., Morris, K., and Thomas, W. K. 2007. Phylogenetic relationships among *Bursaphelenchus* species (Nematoda: Parasitaphelenchidae) inferred from nuclear ribosomal and mitochondrial DNA sequence data. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 43:1185–1197.
- Zeng, Y., Giblin-Davis, R. M., and Ye, W. 2007. Two new species of *Schistonchus* (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae) associated with *Ficus hispida* in China. *Nematology* 9:169–187.
- Zhao, Z. Q., Ye, W. M., Giblin-Davis, R. M., Li, D. M., Thomas, W. K., Davies, K. A., and Riley, I. T. 2008. Morphological and molecular analysis of six *Aphelenchoides* from Australian conifers and their relationship to *Bursaphelenchus* (Fuchs, 1937). *Nematology* 10:663–678.
- Zhuo, K., Cui, R. Q., Ye, W. M., Luo, M., Wang, H. H., Hu, X. N., and Liao, J. L. 2010. Morphological and molecular characterization of *Aphelenchoides fujianensis* n. sp. (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae) from *Pinus massoniana* in China. *Zootaxa* 2509:39–52.